

Semantic transfer as a means of forming medical terms

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Abstract. *The paper gives some results of the analysis of one of the ways of forming medical terms by means of metaphorization. The formation of the meaning of secondary nomination proceeds in the process of rethinking the "previous" meaning of words. This rethinking can occur either on the basis of the noted external similarity of real objects, or as a result of their performance of the same similar functions. Metaphorization in the English medical terminology system is carried out through the activation of meaningful associations in both native English words and words of Greek-Latin origin.*

Keywords: *metaphorization, term formation, meaning, scientific terminology.*

Scientific terminology is the most dynamic part of the lexical and semantic system of the language. Special literature notes that "Terminology is a property of science, technology, politics, that is, the sphere of intellectually organized social reality" [5, p.115]. It occupies a central place in the lexical composition of the sub-languages of science due to the fact that it carries the greatest nominative and informational load in professional speech. In this regard, the ways of forming terms are of particular interest [4, p.95]. Medical scientific terminology is replenished mainly due to the following methods of term formation: morphological, syntactic, and semantic.

In our study, we focused on one of the methods of semantic term formation in medicine, namely, metaphor. Metaphor is a universal phenomenon in the language, which occupies one of the important places in the structure of semantic term formation. A metaphor is always a comparison, mostly hidden. It creates similarity due to two-dimensionality – application to two subjects at the same time. [6, p.202].

The process of metaphorization is not new in the formation of medical terms. It comes from the Middle Ages, therefore metaphorization, although it generates a new term, still uses the words of existing languages [7, p.62]. We analyzed 218 terms formed in medical terminology by metaphorization.

Reinterpretation of the meaning of general literary words and the addition of a new lexical meaning usually occur on the basis of associations that arise in the researcher about the similarity of the phenomenon discovered by him with already known objects, phenomena, processes. These terms perform a cognitive function in research activities [1, p.48].

Exploring the metaphorization of meaning in medical terminology, one should talk about several types of metaphorical transfer: based on the similarity of external signs; based on similarity in function; by contiguity of concepts, and by analogy of concepts [3, p. 510]. In the following examples, we will consider the dominant types of the semantic method of term formation – the formation of a term as a result of transfer by external **similarity and function**.

I. Terms formed on the basis of external similarity are characterized by the fact that a word is used to express the term denoting an object that has external features (shape, size, color, appearance, structure, etc.)

similar to the same features of the object of termination [2, p.113].

The metaphorization of the meaning of a word based on **external similarity**

can be divided according to the following features:

1. **Similarity in shape**, for example "tissue", "gland", "cancer" and some others. Almost all of the above terms are used in the terminology of medicine in terminological phrases, since terms such as "tissue", "gland" have primarily a general medical meaning, and the specification of these terms occurs in combination with the descriptor. For example: "adrenal gland", "thyroid gland"; "fibrous tissue", "neural tissue". This is due to the fact that these terms denote generic concepts that are characterized by sufficient breadth, and since there are various types of tissues and glands in the human body, the descriptor specifies the belonging of the terminological phrase to a certain sublanguage of medicine. For example, the terminological phrase "lacrimal gland" refers to the terminology of ophthalmology, while "anterior lingual gland" refers to the terminology of dentistry.

There is a group of terminological phrases, which include descriptors formed on the basis of metaphorization of meaning. They continue the group of terms formed by metaphorical transfer based on external similarity:

The terminological combination "butterfly fracture" is a fracture in which more than two bone fragments are formed, which in their shape resemble the wings of a butterfly.

2. **Similarity in structure**: "jelly trachoma" – inclusions in the conjunctiva with a gelatinous structure.

3. **Similarity in appearance**: "Geographic keratitis" – a viral lesion of the cornea, in which the transparent cornea acquires a pattern resembling a geographical map.

4. **Similarity in appearance to animals**. For example: "hare lip" – the condition is known as a "hare-lip" because of its resemblance to a hare or rabbit;

"Colibri forceps" – a surgical instrument with very small, curved in the form of a hummingbird beak, branches (tips).

II. Metaphorical transfer based on **similarity in function**. The terms formed by the similarity in functions are characterized by the fact that to express the concept being terminated, a word is used denoting an object, the functions of which are similar to the functions of the terminating object. This is how the following medical terms are formed: "vessel", formed from the Old

Latin *vascellum* – a small vase (diminutive from the Latin *vas*). This meaning is formed on the basis of a metaphor by function, since vessels, figuratively speaking, are the containers for blood in a living organism. The term "orbit" is also formed on the basis of a metaphor for function, since in classical Latin language this word meant a track, that is, the eyeball moves in a certain orbit in an enclosed space.

No less interesting to us is the term "artery" – which was also created by a metaphor for the function: containing air. The term "artery" was created during the period of ancient Greek medicine. Gr. *artēria* (*aer* – air + *tereō* – contain) reflects the misconception of physicians at that time that the arteries contain air. But even today,

this term is present in medical terminology, although the true function of these vessels has been discovered – to supply blood to organs and tissues of a living organism.

Metaphorization in the English medical terminology system is carried out through the activation of meaningful associations in both native English words and words of Greek-Latin origin.

The results of our study showed that the metaphor as one of the semantic methods of terms formation is not widespread in modern terminology of medicine (1.6% of the entire sample) due to its specificity. However, it must be admitted that through semantic methods there is still a replenishment of modern English medical vocabulary.

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